

Supplementary Data

Table S1. One-way ANOVA results for the preliminary antimicrobial activities of non-polar extracts of *Magnolia virginiana* L. flowers.

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
n-Hexane_Extract	Between Groups	312.000	17	18.353	282.353	.000
	Within Groups	2.340	36	.065		
	Total	314.340	53			
Diethyl_Ether_Extract	Between Groups	457.713	17	26.924	381.604	.000
	Within Groups	2.540	36	.071		
	Total	460.253	53			

Table S2. Unpaired independent sample t-test results for the preliminary antimicrobial activities of non-polar extracts of *Magnolia virginiana* L. flowers.

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 29213	Equal variances assumed	.571	.492	-10.445	4	.000	-2.0000	.1915	-2.5316	-1.4684
	Equal variances not assumed			-10.445	3.723	.001	-2.0000	.1915	-2.5476	-1.4524
<i>S. aureus</i> *	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-26.186	4	.000	-4.0000	.1528	-4.4241	-3.5759
	Equal variances not assumed			-26.186	3.920	.000	-4.0000	.1528	-4.4275	-3.5725
MRSA-1*	Equal variances assumed	1.455	.294	-16.803	4	.000	-4.0000	.2380	-4.6609	-3.3391
	Equal variances not assumed			-16.803	3.124	.000	-4.0000	.2380	-4.7408	-3.2592
MRSA-2*	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-14.142	4	.000	-2.0000	.1414	-2.3926	-1.6074
	Equal variances not assumed			-14.142	4.000	.000	-2.0000	.1414	-2.3926	-1.6074
<i>S. epidermidis</i> ATCC 12228	Equal variances assumed	.571	.492	-26.112	4	.000	-5.0000	.1915	-5.5316	-4.4684
	Equal variances not assumed			-26.112	3.723	.000	-5.0000	.1915	-5.5476	-4.4524

<i>S. saprophyticus</i> ATCC 43867	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-21.213	4	.000	-6.0000	.2828	-6.7853	-5.2147
	Equal variances not assumed			-21.213	4.000	.000	-6.0000	.2828	-6.7853	-5.2147
<i>S. pneumoniae</i> ATCC 49619	Equal variances assumed	.364	.579	-9.333	4	.001	-3.0000	.3215	-3.8925	-2.1075
	Equal variances not assumed			-9.333	3.806	.001	-3.0000	.3215	-3.9107	-2.0893
<i>E. faecalis</i> ATCC 29212	Equal variances assumed	1.000	.374	-38.341	4	.000	-7.00000	.18257	-7.50691	-6.49309
	Equal variances not assumed			-38.341	3.448	.000	-7.00000	.18257	-7.54055	-6.45945
<i>B. cereus</i> ATCC 10876	Equal variances assumed	3.200	.148	-13.416	4	.000	-3.00000	.22361	-3.62083	-2.37917
	Equal variances not assumed			-13.416	2.941	.001	-3.00000	.22361	-3.71974	-2.28026
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	Equal variances assumed	3.200	.148	-17.889	4	.000	-4.00000	.22361	-4.62083	-3.37917
	Equal variances not assumed			-17.889	2.941	.000	-4.00000	.22361	-4.71974	-3.28026
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> ATCC 27736	Equal variances assumed	16.000	.016	-20.000	4	.000	-2.00000	.10000	-2.27764	-1.72236
	Equal variances not assumed			-20.000	2.000	.002	-2.00000	.10000	-2.43027	-1.56973
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> ATCC 9027	Equal variances assumed	4.000	.116	-50.229	4	.000	-5.80000	.11547	-6.12060	-5.47940
	Equal variances not assumed			-50.229	2.000	.000	-5.80000	.11547	-6.29683	-5.30317

<i>S. typhimurium</i> ATCC 13311	Equal variances assumed	.571	.492	-15.894	4	.000	-4.00000	.25166	-4.69872	-3.30128
	Equal variances not assumed			-15.894	3.741	.000	-4.00000	.25166	-4.71823	-3.28177
<i>S. flexneri</i> ATCC 12022	Equal variances assumed	12.000	.026	-58.919	4	.000	-9.00000	.15275	-9.42411	-8.57589
	Equal variances not assumed			-58.919	2.000	.000	-9.00000	.15275	-9.65724	-8.34276
<i>P. vulgaris</i> ATCC 6380	Equal variances assumed	4.000	.116	-51.962	4	.000	-6.00000	.11547	-6.32060	-5.67940
	Equal variances not assumed			-51.962	2.000	.000	-6.00000	.11547	-6.49683	-5.50317
<i>P. mirabilis</i> ATCC 29906	Equal variances assumed	14.286	.019	-7.947	4	.001	-2.00000	.25166	-2.69872	-1.30128
	Equal variances not assumed			-7.947	2.000	.015	-2.00000	.25166	-3.08281	-.91719
<i>C. albicans</i> ATCC 10231	Equal variances assumed	1.600	.275	-16.984	4	.000	-5.00000	.29439	-5.81736	-4.18264
	Equal variances not assumed			-16.984	3.298	.000	-5.00000	.29439	-5.89083	-4.10917
<i>A. niger</i> ATCC 6275	Equal variances assumed	3.200	.148	-35.777	4	.000	-8.00000	.22361	-8.62083	-7.37917
	Equal variances not assumed			-35.777	2.941	.000	-8.00000	.22361	-8.71974	-7.28026